

<https://zenodo.org/record/8054635>

A THOUSAND-FOLD OFFERING RITUAL

by Gser mo mtsho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ།

19 June 2023

A Thousand-Fold Offering Ritual was held by monks at my home in Ban ser Community, Mgo mang (Guomaying) Township, Mang rdzong (Guinan) County, Mstho Lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mstho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China on Thursday, May 25, 2023. This involved offering butter lamps, holy water, incense, prostrations, and circumambulation, with each activity being performed a thousand times.

Stong mchod is an important spiritual practice helping practitioners overcome fears and attachments, purify negative karma, and develop compassion and wisdom. The primary purpose of this ritual was to assist my sick grandmother, a devout Buddhist. Despite receiving medical treatment, her condition did not improve, so my family sought hope and healing from religious practice. My family invited six monks from Klu tshang Monastery to conduct the ritual. My family gave 300 RMB and offered *kha btags* 'strip of silk'. The total cost of the ritual was approximately 4,000 RMB.

TIBETAN TERMS

ban ser བན་སེར།

klu tshang ལྷ་ཚང།

kha btags ཁ་བྲགགས།

mang rzung མང་རྫོང།

mgo mang མགོ་མང།

mtso lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།

mtso sngon མཚོ་སྟོན།

sha rgya ཤ་རྒྱ།

stong mchod ལྷོང་མཚོང།

CHINESE TERMS

Guinan 贵南

Guomaying 过马营

Hainan 海南

<https://archive.org/details/pilgrimage-to-khri-ka-by-gser-mo-mtsho>

PILGRIMAGE TO KHRI KA

by Gser mo mtsho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ།

19 June 2023, 15'02"

On Monday, May 22, 2023, I used an iPhone 12 Pro Max to record the pilgrimage of my grandmother, Kar mo rgyal (b. 1937); mother, Rgya kho (b. 1964); and one of my uncles to the Jo jo lha khang (Zhenzhu si) and Lha kar po (Zhangfo si), located in Khri Ka (Guide) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. Our journey started at our home in Ban ser Community, Mgo mang (Guomaying) Township, Mang rdzong (Guinan) County, approximately 65 km from Khri ka. We went there in my uncle's vehicle.

My grandmother married Bsod noms when she was 16. They divorced when she was 23. She remarried at the age of 25 and had four children. My grandmother has suffered from high blood pressure, causing hearing loss and headaches, since mid-April 2023. My family members thought going on pilgrimage might lessen her suffering and make her feel better spiritually. Thus, we decided to visit those two religious sites in Khri ka.

My grandmother fell ill the day before we left, and my family stayed up all night caring for her. To her delight, my grandmother's hearing improved the day after the pilgrimage, and her headaches vanished. She credits this improvement to Buddha's positive intervention, believing that the monastery visits played a crucial role. She also fulfilled her wish to circumambulate those temples.

TIBETAN TERMS

ban ser བན་སེར།
 bsod noms བསོད་ནམས།
 gser mo mtsho གསེར་མོ་མཚོ།
 jo jo lha khang ཇོ་ཇོ་ལྷ་ཁང།

kar mo rgyal དཀར་མོ་རྒྱལ།
 khri ka ཁྲི་ཀ།
 lha kar po ལྷ་དཀར་པོ།
 mang rdzong མང་རྫོང།
 mgo mang མགོ་མང།
 mstho sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།

mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།

Guide 贵德

Hainan 海南

CHINESE TERMS

Qinghai 青海

Zhenzhu si 珍珠寺

Zhangfo si 长佛寺

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<https://archive.org/details/sonny-80-year-old-celebration>

AN EIGHTY-YEAR CELEBRATION FOR A STAG MA TIBETAN MAN by Bkra shis rgya mtsho འཇམ་ཤེས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།

21 March 2023, 1.05:36

On Saturday, January 21, 2023, an 80-year celebration was held for Stag ma, the 30th day of the 12th lunar month, 2022. From 9 AM to 2 PM, I participated in the celebration, which was held in #1, Wa shur Village, Thang mgo (Tanggu) Town, 'Ba' rdzong (Tongde) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China.

Photographer, writer, editor: Bkra shis rgya mtsho (Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措) using an iPhone 12 Pro Max.

The main character

Stag ma (Stag phrug thar) was born in 1944 in #3 Brigade Klu lung Village. When he was 18, he married Rin chen mtsho (Ri mtsho, b. 1942) and moved to #1 Brigade Wa shur Village. They had three children: Dga' rab rdo rje (b. 1964), Rdo rje sgröl ma (b. 1968), and Phur ba skyabs (b. 1980). Stag ma lived with his younger son's (Phur ba skyabs) family. Stag ma is my (Bkra shis rgya mtsho) maternal uncle. He was a locally famous hunter.

Eighty-year celebration

Historically and locally, there were four celebration parties during a person's life – a birthday party, a 3-year-old haircutting party, a wedding party, and an 80-year celebration. On the day of the last

celebration, on the 1st, 3rd, or 13th day of the 1st lunar month, the celebrant gets up in the early morning, shaves, cuts their hair, washes their face, and puts on such new clothes as a blue sash, a white shirt, a white felt or fox-fur hat, a traditional lambskin or sheepskin robe, and Tibetan-style leather boots. They prepare to welcome visitors before sunrise when neighbors send New Year gifts.

Parents tell their children to ask the celebrant for good wishes and longevity blessings. Tea bricks, white silk scarves, Tibetan cakes, and *rgyal bo* bread are typical gifts. The 8-year-old typically exchanges a silk scarf with those bringing gifts, signifying, "I give my age to you, and may you live 100 years.

"Traditionally, neighbors, close friends, sworn brothers, and close relatives attended this celebration. Historically, such celebrations were rare, but they are more common today, thanks to longer life spans.

Family condition

Stag ma's family at the time of the celebration included Rin chen mtsho (Ri mtsho, b. 1942), Stag ma (b. 1944), Phur ba skyabs (b. 1980), daughter-in-law (Mtsho skyid yag, b.1977), grandson (Gsang bdag rdo rje, b. 1998), granddaughter (Bsod noms dbang mo, b. 2000), granddaughter (Chos mtsho yag, b.2002), and grandson ('Jam dbyangs rig pa'i rdo rje, b. 2009). The family had 700 *mu* (46.9 hectares) of winter pasture, 86 *mu* (5.8 hectares), 20 *mu* (1.3 hectares) of cultivated fields in the summer pasture, 220 sheep, 100 yaks, two horses, vehicles (Ford. a Toyota taxi, a truck), two 豪爵 magnate, a bungalow (9.9*5.9 sq.m., 19.8* 22 sq.m. yard) in Wa shur Village, a bungalow (9.9*5.9 sq.m., 19.8* 22 sq.m. yard) at Kho rgya New Village, and an 84 square meter apartment in the local 'Ba' rdzong (Tongde) New County Town.

Preparation and expenditure

A Mongolian sheepskin robe from Sog rdzong County (Henan), Rma lho (Huangnan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture for Stag ma cost 10,000 RMB. Seven sheep carcasses (0.5 kg of mutton cost 31 RMB for a total mutton cost of ~ 13,000 RMB, 300 tea bricks

at 25 RMB each (7,500 RMB), and apples, oranges, jujube, persimmons, plums, mangoes, vegetables, candies, and other items totaling ~10,000 RMB.

Twenty days before the celebration day, family members were busy preparing. Neighbors came to help fry bread, prepare dumplings and Tibetan cakes, and send oral WeChat invitations to the village WeChat group, the tribe's tantric monk groups (a son is a tantric monk), and certain relatives in other villages. Thirty-four monks and Tantric monks, all from the same tribe, joined the party to chant from 9:30 AM to 2 PM. The host family gave each monk 100 RMB, a tea brick, and a white silk scarf. All attendees, except the monks, presented gifts of a tea brick and white scarf. An estimated 400 attendees were at the celebration. Attendees gave cash gifts ranging from 50-2,000 RMB and such items as bottles of liquor, Tibetan cakes, tea bricks, Tibetan woolen items, hand prayer wheels, and traditional scripture volumes. The total cost of the celebration was 40,000 RMB. The value of the gifts was 35,000 RMB.

Appreciation

Thanks to Stag ma son (Dga' rab rdo rje, a Tantric monk, b. 1944) and grandson (Gsang bdag rdo rje, b. 1998) for providing information.

TIBETAN TERMS

'ba' rdzong འབའ་རྫོང་།

'jam dbyangs rig pa'i rdo

rje འཇམ་དབྱངས་རིག་པའི་རྗེ།

bkra shis rgya mtsho

བཀ་ཤིས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།

bsod nams dbang mo

བསོད་ནམས་དབང་མོ།

chos mtsho yag ཚོས་མཚོ་ཡག

dga' rab rdo rje དགའ་རབ་རྗེ།

gsang bdag rdo rje

གསང་བདག་རྗེ།

kho rgya ཁོ་རྒྱ།

klu lung ལུ་ལུང་།

mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྗོ།

mtsho skyid yag མཚོ་སྐྱིད་ཡག

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྐོན།

phur ba skyabs ཕུར་བརྒྱལ་ས།

rdo rje sngrol ma རྗེ་རྗེ་སྐྱོལ་མ།

ri mtsho རི་མཚོ།

rin chen mtsho རིན་ཆེན་མཚོ།	Hainan 海南
rma lho རྩ་ལྷོ།	Haojue 豪爵
sog rdzong སོག་རྫོང་།	Henan 河南
stag ma ལྷག་མ།	Huangnan 黄南
stag phrug thar ལྷག་ཕུག་ཐར།	mu 亩
thang mgo ཐང་མགོ།	Qinghai 青海
wa shur བ་ཤུར།	Tanggu 唐谷
	Tongde 同德
CHINESE TERMS	Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措

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<https://archive.org/details/glorry-to-the-deities>

GLORY TO THE DEITIES!

by 'Jam dbyangs skyabs འཇམ་དབྱངས་སྐུབས། (Jiayangjian 加羊尖)

30 March 2023, 57'06"

'Jam dbyangs skyabs (Jambo, b. 1997) made this film on 21 September 2022. The film begins with Jambo in a car heading to the family pasture to pick up milk in Skya ga 'Magpie' Valley, Khang sar Township, in the south of Gcig sgril County, about fifty kilometers from the county town. The family will offer a one-day meal for *dbyar gnas*[1] 'summer retreat' to Stag lung dgon ka dag spros bral gling Monastery in Stag lung Valley, Khang sar Township in the south of Gcig sgril County, six kilometers from the county town.

Three Tibetan women who began milking yaks at six AM are featured. Moonlight helps them see as they milked yaks for two hours.

While women were milking the yaks, Jambo chatted with the women. One talked about a dream she had. The women talked about livestock, such as an orphan calf and twin milking yaks.

When they were about to finish milking, the younger woman's husband got up, dressed his son, and took him to the yak enclosure so he could see medicating the calves. They also ear-tagged the calves.

Medicating calves and milking the yaks finished at the same time.

A woman drove the milking yaks from the yak enclosure to graze.

An older woman poured all the milk into a big plastic container and put it in the car. When they noticed an airplane, they yelled, "See, there's an airplane!"

None of the three women had traveled by air or train, so seeing an airplane above them was exciting.

A man drove the car with three men to Mtha' ba 'community near the monastery' where they boiled the milk.

They needed to make an offering the next day of a one-day meal, so they took the milk to the monastery's big kitchen and prepared *dbyar gnas*. They cleaned the kitchen when they finished and went to the assembly hall to listen to *bla ma* and monks chanting. The *dge skos* 'monastic disciplinarian' gave them *mdud pa* 'holy knots', a large piece of yellow silk, a picture of a local *bla ma*, and *ril bu* 'holy pills' (containing sacred substances blessed by a *bla ma* and monks).

In the end, they went to offer incense. The monastery restricts tossing *rlung rta* 'wind horses'¹ while offering incense. Instead, they flung liquor skyward.

Women make a huge contribution in preparing milk and butter. Cooking *dbyar gnas*² is a men's thing. Women are not allowed to enter the monastery's big kitchen nor offer incense. No local woman would say, "I want to cook *dbyar gnas*. You men milk the yaks."

Women accept cooking *dbyar gnas* as a male duty and milking yaks in the early morning as a female duty.

During *dbyar gnas*, women, including nuns, are forbidden to enter monasteries.

Men offer incense while shouting, "Glory to the deities!"

¹ For more on *rlung rta*, see <https://bit.ly/3QmVxGi> 8 January 2023.

² For more on *dbyar gnas*, see <https://bit.ly/3vHIXbo> 7 January 2023.

TIBETAN TERMS

'jam dbyangs skyabs

འཇམ་དབྱངས་སྐྱབས།

bla ma ལྷ་མ།

dbyar gnas དབྱར་གནས།

dge skos དགོ་སྐོས།

gcig sgril གཅིག་སྒྲིལ།

khang sar ཁང་སར།

mdud pa མདུད་པ།

mtha' ba མཐའ་བ།

ril bu རིལ་བུ།

rlung rta ལུང་རྟ།

skya ga སྐྱ་ག།

stag lung dgon ka dag spros

bral gling

སྐྱ་ག་ལུང་དགོན་ཀ་དག་སྐྱོས་བའ་གླིང་།

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https://archive.org/details/Mdo_ba_Township_Town_Reb_gong

MDO BA TOWNSHIP TOWN, TONGREN COUNTY,
RMA LHO TIBETAN AUTONOMOUS PREFECTURE,
MSTHO SNGON PROVINCE, PR CHINA

by Chos skyong skyabs ཚོས་སྐྱོང་སྐྱབས།

2019, 10'22"

Now a town, this film shows the Town Center and surrounding areas during a time of rapid social transformation in this pastoral area.

མཚོ་ཐོན་ཁིང་ཚེན་མ་སྐྱོ་བོད་རིགས་རང་སྐྱོང་ཁུལ་གྱི་ཐུན་རིན་ཚོང་མདོ་བ་ཁང་།

Mdo ba Township Town, Tongren County, Rma lho Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mstho sngon Province, PR China

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<https://archive.org/details/g.yang-res-skyid-mends-slightshot>

G.YANG RES SKYID MENDS A TIBETAN
SLIGHTSHOT IN MGO LOG (GOLOK) by

'Jam dbyangs skyabs འཇམ་དབྱངས་སྐྱབས། (Jiayangjian 加羊尖)

17 January 2023, 6'32"

This video was made on 15 January 2023. G.yang res skyid lives in her family's winter pasture, Rdo ra Valley, Gsa' skor Tribe, Khang sar Township Town, Gcig sgril County, Mgo log Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon Province, RP China.

G.yang res skyid (b. 1990) mends her slingshot with *rtsid skud* 'thread' (yarn made of coarse yak hair). She spins thread using a "chopstick" spindle and starts sewing her slingshot.

G.yang res skyid never attended school. The oldest of four children, her parents kept her at home because they needed her help to look after their livestock. Her two younger sisters went to school, and her younger brother became a monk at six, which was her parents' and grandparents' idea: "Ye shes bzang po (b. 1996) is the only son, so he should become a monk."

G.yang res skyid has three children and has spent her entire life on her family's pastures, rarely leaving her local home community. Her hard work for her family is impressive! Herding livestock and doing house chores are work she never complains about.

G.yang res skyid sewing her slingshot was not a performance. She is accustomed to sewing with *rtsid skud*. Nowadays, people buy all kinds of "thread," but *rtsid skud* is not on that list. More importantly, few people now sew things by themselves.

G.yang res skyid is one of the few people who try to be self-sufficient and not rely on others. When G.yang res skyid discovered her slingshot was torn, she thought of mending it and not buying a new one.

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<https://archive.org/details/dolmas-film>.

MILKING TIBETAN YAKS, MAKING BUTTER AND
CHEESE 2022, G.YANG SHAR (YAXIU) VILLAGE
G.YU DKA' 'OM LUNG (YIKEWULAN) TOWNSHIP,
RKANG TASHA (GANGCHA) COUNTY, PR CHINA by

Sgrol ma lha mo སྐྱོལ་མ་ལ་མོ། (Zhuo ma la mao 卓玛拉毛; Dolma Lha mo)
2022 14'38"

Filmed in G.yang shar (Yaxiu) Village G.yu dka' 'om lung (Yikewulan) Township, Rkang tasha (Gangcha) County, China. Women milk yaks and make butter and cheese in summer. Filmed by Dol ma lha mo (Dloma Lhamo) 10 July 2022.

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<https://archive.org/details/yul-shul-film-2022>

**THANG SKYID VILLAGE, 'BA' DGON TOWNSHIP,
CHU DMAR LEB COUNTY, YUL SHUL TIBETAN
AUTONOMOUS PREFECTURE, MTSO SNGON
(QINGHAI) PROVINCE, PR CHINA**

by Bkra shis rab rgyas བཏཱ་ཤིས་རབ་རྒྱལ།

31 December 2022, 13'37"

Filmed in Thang skyid Village, 'Ba' dgon Township, Chu dmar leb County, Yul shul Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China, featuring yaks on the grassland. Collecting caterpillar fungus near the Yangtse River. Filmed by Bkra shis rab rgyas, 20 June 2022.

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<https://archive.org/details/yul-shul-tibetan-autonomous-prefecture-2022>

**MAKE OFFERINGS TO THE HIGH GODS AND GIVE
ALMS TO THE LOW SIX BEINGS - YUL SHUL 2022
YAR DKON MCHO G LA MCHOD PA MAR RIGS DRUG
LA SBYIN PA ཡར་དཀོན་མཚོག་ལ་མཚོད་པ་མར་རིགས་དུག་ལ་སྦྱིན་པ།**

by Bkra shis rab rgyas བཏཱ་ཤིས་རབ་རྒྱལ།

2022, 6'02"

On the fifteenth day of the seventh lunar month (Tibetan Calendar) in our community (Thang skyid (Tongji) Village, 'Ba' dgon (Bagan) Township, Chu dmar leb (Qumalai) County, Yul shul (Yushu) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China) local people chanted scriptures more than usual, went to 'Ba' dgon (Bagan) Township Town, and circumambulated the stupas there. It is also a time when some in Yul shul Prefecture buy fish from Chinese people and put them in the 'Bri chu (Yangtze River), or other rivers, buy livestock (set them free and never kill them), give money to beggars, put the fish they buy into rivers, and give food to homeless dogs.

This is *yar dkon mchog la mchod pa mar ri drug la spyin pa*.

A monk relative instructed us in Thang skyid to make small balls with *rtsam pa*. He also asked Mother to add fresh milk to the small balls of *rtsam pa*. After he finished chanting at the 'Bri chu, we made a yak-dung fire and added juniper. After chanting for a few minutes, the monk poured milk into a plate with small *rtsam pa* balls and poured the plate's contents into the 'Bri chu.

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<https://archive.org/details/traditional-tibetan-wedding-copy>

A TRADITIONAL TIBETAN WEDDING

by Bkra shis rgya mtsho བཀ་ཤིས་རྒྱ་མཚོ་ (Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措)

January 28, 2021-February 10, 2022, 2 hours, 28 minutes

Bkra shis rgya mtsho used an iPhone 12 Pro Max)

Part-One

This documentary focuses on a traditional wedding celebration in a herding family at 35 °9'45" latitude, 100°26'22" longitude, 3,351 MASL in #3 Brigade, Hwo thog sum dbrag Valley, Klu lung Village, Thang mgo (Tanggu) Town, 'Ba' rdzong (Tongde) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. I participated throughout the 14-day celebration.

On the 5th day of the first lunar month, 2022, a celebration was held for the groom, Bdud mgon skyabs, and the bride, Choe bzang sgrol ma.

In the early 2020s, most locals held weddings in 'Ba' rdzong County Town restaurants. However, some families divided into two groups. One group held a wedding celebration at home in the traditional way, and the other held a wedding celebration in a restaurant. This family held wedding celebrations at home.

Main Characters

Bdud mgon skyabs (b. 1995) in Klu lung Village. In 2019, he graduated from Mtsho sngon Normal University and taught Tibetan at 'Od gsal Tibetan Primary School, 'Od gsal Township, Dar legs County, Mgo log Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture.

Choe bzang sgröl ma (b.1996) Dung dkar Village, Tang mgo Town graduated in 2018 from Mtsho sngon Normal University and taught mathematics at 'Ba' rdzong Boarding Primary School, 'Ba' rdzong County Town.

Family Members

Bdud mgon skyabs is my maternal cousin. His family has ten members: his father (Smin grol, Ngag dbang smin grol, b.1965), mother (Skal khao, Skal bzang sgröl ma, b. 1970), uncle (Blo bzang tshul khirms, b. 1971, a Bde chen Monastery monk), older brother (Blo bzang dpal ldan (b. 1992), sister-in-law (Bsod nams sgröl ma (b. 1992, from Rgya bo Village, Tang mgo Town), younger sister (Ye shes mtsho (b. 1996, graduated from Mtsho sngon Qaidam (Chaidamu) Vocational and Technical College in 2019), nephew (Yum skyabs rgyal, b. 2016), and Tshe dpal mkhar (b. 2018).

Family Conditions

The family has 370 mu (24.66 hectares) of winter pasture, 17 mu (1.13 hectares) of summer pasture, 14 mu (hectares 0.93) of farmland, 80 yaks, 100 sheep, a black goat, a brown dog, a black cat, vehicles (Rongwie 360, Lifan 330), 2 motorcycles (Qianjiang, Wuyangbentian), a 3-wheel agriculture vehicle, a walking tractor crusher, two greenhouses (108m² and 82m²), a 132m² flat on the winter pasture, and a bungalow (9.9*5.9m², 19.8* 22m² yard), and an 84m² apartment in 'Ba' rdzong New County Town.

Preparation and expenditure

Months before the wedding celebrations, a local tailor was located and asked to sew traditional garments such as lambskin robes for the new couples. Ornaments, for example, a 60g gold necklace, a

coral necklace, a pair of 9g gold earrings, a gold finger ring, a silver milk bucket holder, a teardrop-shaped silver panel, and a hair-ornament were bought for the bride in the local County Town market for approximately 47,000 RMB and paid by the groom's family.

After preparations, the groom's father and one of his cousins brought items for the bride, including a lambskin robe, a cloth robe, a hat, and ornaments. Because of local community rules, these items and did not exceed 3,013 RMB cash (the brideprice), 13 bottles of liquor, three large pieces of silk/cloth (the size of a traditional Tibetan robe), and a white silk scarf.

Other expenses (RMB):

Mutton	3,550
Plates 1	215
Tables	1,600
Beverages (liquor, non-alcoholic drinks, red wine)	5,065
Fruit	380
Granulated sugar	120
Vegetables and noodles	150
Metal stove	1,360
Coal	140

Total	13,580 RMB

January 28, 2021, neighbors and relatives came to help, including Tshe ring sgrol ma, TA re, Phag mo, Bde skyid 'tsho, Sgrol ma yag, Chos thar rgyal, Lha snang rgyal, Nyi ma lha mo, 'Bum phyug skyid, Dbang kho, Tshul rnam, and Rta kho. They chopped 50 kg of meat to make boiled dumplings and steamed stuffed buns. Family members were busy making red bread, Tibetan cakes, and boiling mutton for displays on tables in front of guests. Blo bzang dpal ldan was busy with other men operating the 3-wheeler to borrow tea tables, carpets, seat cushions, chairs, plates, and white fabric tents from neighbors.

Participants in the wedding celebrations included

representatives from 199 households (255 people). 113 households from the local village sent representatives, Klu lung Village 86 households from different villages, including Rgya bo, Dang po, Ho thog, Wa shur, Tho si, Rde'u dkar, Gle ba, the groom's classmates, and 16 households sent gifts of red packet money through WeChat.

Attendees gave cash gifts ranging from 50-1,500 RMB and such items as bottles of liquor, Tibetan cakes, boxes of biscuits, Tibetan wool items, and white silk scarves. The total cost of the celebration was approximately 63,580 RMB. The value of the gifts was about 31,250 RMB.

Part-Two

Wedding Celebrations

There are two types of local marriage patterns: arrangement and romantic marriage. In the past, most children followed their parents' marriage arrangements. Parents thus had a significant obligation to choose suitable spouses for their children, particularly the bride for their son, and hold auspicious wedding celebrations showcasing the family's position in the community. Parents considered their children's marriage before the age of fifteen. Important concerns in choosing their children's spouses included pure bones (no body odor) and family protector deity (between different tribes, offerings to different protector deities were thought to bring misfortune). The last taboo concerns the harmony of zodiac animals. Therefore, according to traditional divination: the following pairs conflict, tiger-monkey, hare-rooster, dragon-dog, snake-pig, horse-rat, and sheep-cow. The harmonious pairs included pig-sheep-hare, dog-horse-tiger, rooster-cow-snake, and rat-dragon-monkey.

On the wedding day, a woman was chosen to offer tea in front of the bride at the yak enclosure, and another woman took the bride's horse reins. The contemporary version of this is a woman who touched the bride's hat and tied a white-silk scarf to the driver's side car mirror of the car with the bride). This woman was chosen according to the zodiac animal concerns mentioned above.

Parents investigated the background of the bride's family and chose an eloquent matchmaker from their relatives or community to ask the bride's parents and their elder relatives if they agreed to their child's marriage. Both sides consulted local religious leaders to divine or astrologers to examine zodiac-animal compatibility.

On the wedding day, relatives participated in congratulating the new couple. Meanwhile, relatives pitched a new black yak hair tent for the couple, collected items, especially furniture, and gave the new couple yaks, sheep, and horses.

Recently, most marriage partners have chosen free-choice marriage. On this wedding day in the early morning, after chanting the ritual of family deities to expel misfortune by the family ritual specialist, Rang gsal, the groom and 3 escorts visited the bride's home and soon returned. The bride, with 14 escorts, then came to the groom's home. A singer sang a traditional song to welcome the bride and escorts. After several minutes, the escorts and the groom's side women engaged in several rounds of antiphonal singing. When escorts were ready to leave, the family host gave each 200 RMB in cash and a white silk scarf.

Part-Three

After the wedding

After the wedding celebration, family members and some neighbors busily returned items borrowed from neighbors. On February 10, 2022, four escorts (including the bride's father and the bride) brought the dowry to her family and relatives, who gave her such items as lambskin robes, sheepskin robes, Tibetan wool robes, 2 cloth robes, 3 sashes, 3 traditional shirts, a 2g gold necklace, gold earrings, a 3g gold ring, silver necklace, diamond necklace, and shoes. The bride's clothes were put on a line in the enclosure to display to neighbors and participants. The bride's gifts such as fruit, Tibetan cakes, and biscuits were divided among participants.

The bride's father offered liquor three times to the air. He praised all deities in his family and said, "I'm so glad our children

do not choose external spouses - particularly different religious believers. At contemporary schools, some children choose to marry partners from different ethnicities. I have nothing to say about my daughter's choice. I definitely agree with this wedding.”

After this day, neighbors and relatives invited the bride to their home and gave presents. Most families gave 100-300 RMB. According to local custom, the neighbors and relatives first invited the bride. Afterward, she could visit their families randomly.

Acknowledgment

My cousins, Blo bzang dpal ldan and Bdud mgon skyabs, and my maternal uncle (Smin grol) provided information that helped complete this film and documentation. .

TIBETAN TERMS

'ba' rdzong འབའ་རྫོང་།
 'bum phyug skyid འབམ་ཕྱུག་སྐྱིད།
 'od gsal འོད་གསལ།
 bde chen བདེ་ཆེན།
 bde skyid 'tsho བདེ་སྐྱིད་མཚོ།
 bdud mgon skyabs བདད་མགོན་སྐྱའམ།
 bkra shis rgya mtsho བཀའ་ཤིས་རྒྱ་མཚོ།
 blo bzang dpal ldan ལྷོ་བཟང་དཔལ་ལྷན།
 blo bzang tshul khrim ལྷོ་བཟང་ཚུལ་ཁྲིམས།
 bsod nams sgrol ma བསོད་ནམས་སྐྱོལ་མ།
 choe bzang sgrol ma ཚོས་བཟང་སྐྱོལ་མ།
 chos thar rgyal ཚོས་ཐར་རྒྱལ།
 dang po དང་པོ།
 dar legs དར་ལགས།
 dbang kho དབང་ཁོ།
 dung dkar དུང་དཀར།
 gle ba རྩེ་བ།
 ho thog ཧོ་ཐོག

hwo thog sum dbrag ཧོ་ཐོག་སུམ་དབྱག
 klu lung ལུ་ལུང་།
 lha snang rgyal ལྷ་སྣང་རྒྱལ།
 mgo log མགོ་ལོག
 mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།
 mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།
 ngag dbang smin grol འག་དབང་སྐྱེན་གྲོལ།
 nyi ma lha mo ཉི་མ་ལྷ་མོ།
 phag mo ཕག་མོ།
 rang gsal རང་གསལ།
 rde'u dkar རེའུ་དཀར།
 rdo mo རོ་མོ།
 rgya bo རྒྱ་བོ།
 rta kho རྩ་ཁོ།
 sgrol ma yag སྐྱོལ་མ་ཡག
 skal bzang sgrol ma སྐལ་བཟང་སྐྱོལ་མ།
 skal khao སྐལ་ཁོ།
 smin grol སྐྱེན་གྲོལ།
 ta re ཐཱ་རེ།
 thang mgo ཐང་མགོ།
 tho si ཐོ་སི།

tshe dpal mkhar ཚེ་དཔལ་མཁའ་མཁའ་།
tshe ring sgröl ma ཚེ་རིང་སྒྲོལ་མཁའ་།
tshul rnam ཚུལ་རྣམ།
wa shur ལ་ཤུར།
ye shes mtsho ཡེ་ཤེས་མཚོ།
yum skyabs rgyal ཡུམ་སྐྱའབས་རྒྱལ།

CHINESE TERMS

Chaidamu 柴达木
Hainan 海南
Lifan 力凡
Qianjiang 钱江
Qinghai 青海
Rongwie 荣威
Tangu 塘谷
Tongde 同德
Wuyangbentian 五羊本田
Zhaxijiancuo 扎西尖措